

Femtosecond Fieldoscopy

For Super-Resolution Label-Free Microscopy

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Accessing complete electric field information of a laser pulse interacting with a medium at visible to near-infrared (near-petahertz) frequencies has traditionally required complex laboratory systems operating in vacuum conditions. Recent advancements, however, have enabled the measurement of electric fields at near-petahertz frequencies in ambient air. This capability is critical for understanding ultrafast phenomena and for achieving quantitative detection of molecular species in various samples. This article introduces Femtosecond Fieldoscopy, a field-resolved detection technique for label-free spectroscopy and microscopy. This approach delivers exceptional detection sensitivity and dynamic range at petahertz bandwidths by combining attosecond temporal resolution with temporal isolation of target molecular responses from environmental and excitation pulse

effects. Furthermore, Femtosecond Fieldoscopy holds promise for achieving sub-diffraction spatial resolution, opening new horizons for high-precision label-free spectro-microscopy.

Introduction

Vibrational microscopy is a powerful tool for non-perturbative, label-free identification of complex molecular compositions. It offers intrinsic chemical selectivity due to the specific vibrational frequencies of different molecules, known as molecular fingerprints. Among various label-free imaging techniques, stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) in the near-infrared spectral range stands out because of its low water absorption cross-section, high penetration depth, high spatial resolution, and linear relationship with

molecular concentration. However, the spatial resolution of SRS label-free images is limited by the diffraction limit of the excitation pulse. In recent years, various strategies have been developed to achieve super-resolution SRS images by using Raman-active labels, structuring the excitation beams, exciting higher-order nonlinearity, or applying computational reconstruction methods, albeit with trade-offs. Figure 1 shows that the spatial resolution for current label-free SRS imaging exceeds 200 nm. The gray area in Figure 1 highlights an unexplored frontier in non-perturbative, label-free spectro-microscopy, where achieving resolutions beyond this threshold remains a significant scientific challenge.

Field-resolved detection has been a powerful method in the mid-infrared and terahertz spectral ranges, as it allows for the direct measurement of

light-matter interactions in sub-cycle regimes, capturing both amplitude and phase information. However, this method has not been employable in SRS detection due to the near-petahertz (PHz) frequency of excitation pulses in stimulated Raman interactions. For decades, attosecond streaking, which was awarded the Nobel Prize in 2023, has been the sole method to probe the electric field of light at frequencies approaching PHz. Yet, the requirement for vacuum conditions in attosecond streaking limits its applicability in biological contexts. Over the last few years, various techniques have been developed that enable near-PHz field-resolved light detection in ambient air. Among these techniques, electro-optic sampling (EOS) stands out for its unparalleled detection sensitivity and intrinsic sub-diffraction spatial resolution when used for imaging. In this article, we discuss how EOS can detect the molecular response in the short wavelength infrared and SRS, and how this concept advances the frontiers of non-perturbative, super-resolution, label-free microscopy.

Electro-Optic Sampling at Near-Petahertz

In EOS, the electric field of a sample pulse is probed by a short pulse with a higher central frequency and a shorter temporal duration. When the two pulses interact in a phase-matched nonlinear medium, a sum frequency signal is generated, with its strength being proportional to the electric field strength of the sample pulse. Due to the broad spectral bandwidth of the interacting pulses, part of the probe pulses' spectrum overlaps with the generated sum frequency spectrum. This overlapped region is filtered spectrally and detected by a balanced detector. The electric field of the sample pulse is captured by temporally scanning the probe pulse over the sample pulse. The probe pulse plays a crucial role in EOS; it facilitates the upconversion of the signal and serves as a local oscillator, which enhances the detection signal-to-noise ratio and detection sensitivity through heterodyne detection, making the shot noise of the probe pulse the primary source of noise. By upconverting the signal's spectral bandwidth to higher frequencies, EOS enables the use of silicon detectors for broadband near-infrared detection.

Figure 1: State-of-the-art label-free stimulated Raman microscopes. This figure compares the spatial resolution of these advanced microscopes. Black stars represent the SRS microscopes, while red stars indicate coherent anti-Stokes Raman scattering images. Increasing the excitation pulse frequency enhances spatial resolution, but also raises the risk of damage to soft tissue. The area marked by the red arrow highlights the optimum operation point.

Figure 2: Near-Petahertz femtosecond fieldoscopy. (a) An ultrashort optical pulse impulsively excites all the in-resonance molecules along its beam path. The molecules in the cuvette represent the sample under test, while the surrounding molecules represent the environmental ones. As the transmitted field propagates, it accumulates the combined molecular responses of both the sample and the environment. A higher-frequency ultrashort probe pulse is employed for up-conversion, generating a delay-dependent signal in a quadratic medium. The measured electric field captures the excitation pulse, the liquid's picosecond-scale response, and the atmospheric gases' nanosecond-scale response. Time filtering analysis separates these into short-lived liquid and long-lived gas responses. (b) Biologically relevant vibrational modes in the near-infrared range correspond to compounds such as proteins, carbohydrates, lipids, polyphenols, and alcohols. Vibrational bands, including stretching ("str") and bending ("bend"), are detailed in the legend. First and second overtones [1,2] and combination bands (+) are noted. The image is taken from reference [2].

Figure 3: Femtosecond laser interaction with the central nervous system of zebrafish. (a) The damage threshold peak intensities are presented at various wavelengths and repetition rates. (b) The peak intensity for different irradiation wavelengths is maintained below the damage threshold, and the irradiation time is increased. It was noted that the damage site expanded gradually with increasing irradiation time at 343 nm and 515 nm. No damage was observed after 900 seconds of irradiation at 1030 nm. (c) The damage threshold peak intensity for wild type and differently labeled (*elavl3:GFP-F* and *elavl3:RasmKate2*) transgenic zebrafish larvae. (d) Top: Bright field image of the spinal cord of transgenically labeled zebrafish larvae after irradiation with 30 mW laser pulses at 1030 nm and at 2 MHz repetition rates. Bottom: Subsequent regrowth of white matter tracts post-irradiation. Scale bars: 50 μm . In panels (a, c), the error bars represent standard deviation. The figure is reproduced from reference [9].

Femtosecond Fieldsocopy

Field-resolved detection at near-peta-hertz frequencies provides exceptional detection sensitivity, bandwidth, and dynamic range while enabling attosecond temporal and sub-diffraction spatial resolution. In a novel scheme that we call "Femtosecond Fieldsocopy" (Fig. 2), ultrashort excitation laser pulses impulsively excite the in-resonance molecular composition of a sample. Subsequently, vibrational coherence is initiated at the trailing edge of the excitation pulses, decaying exponentially at a rate proportional to the vibrational dephasing time. The transmitted electric field contains the ultrashort excitation pulse, the sample's delayed response spanning several picoseconds, and a long-lasting response from atmospheric gases that lasts for hundreds of nanoseconds. One can access broadband information about molecular composition and concentration via field-resolved detection of the molecular response in the time domain and subsequent Fourier transformation. Specifically, by Fourier transforming the decaying trail of the electric field containing the pure molecular response, one gains spectroscopic information with unprecedented sensitivity and dynamic range, as this approach temporally gates the molecular response from the main excitation pulse. Femtosecond Fieldsocopy has recently been used to detect overtone, Raman, and combination bands in various liquid samples [2-4]. Furthermore, several techniques have been

developed to accelerate the method for real-time detection [5-7] and extend its capabilities to label-free imaging [8].

Towards Super-Resolution Label-Free Imaging

The spatial resolution in label-free SRS microscopy is constrained by the diffraction limit of the Raman excitation pulses. Increasing the frequency of the excitation pulses enhances spatial resolution. However, the probability of damage also increases with the irradiation frequency, limiting in vivo microscopy. Our recent study revealed a different and nonlinear damage mechanism at 1030 nm, which has a higher damage threshold than UV pulses, making this wavelength range suitable for non-invasive in vivo interactions with biological samples (Fig. 3) [9]. However, imaging at longer wavelengths results in reduced spatial resolution. Femtosecond Fieldsocopy provides a solution to this challenge. In Femtosecond Fieldsocopy, the detected molecular response is confined to the overlapped area of the excitation and probe pulses. Here, the spatial resolution of the SRS image is determined by the diffraction limit of the short-wavelength probe pulses. Consequently, the Raman response of a sample can be coherently excited by femtosecond laser pulses in the near-infrared range, while the spatial gating of the EOS achieves spatial resolution at the sub-diffraction limit of the excitation Raman pulses [10].

Outlook

Label-free SRS microscopy enables imaging molecules in their natural state; however, its spatial resolution is limited by the diffraction limit of Raman excitation pulses, which restricts the unperturbed detection of small molecules. For instance, detecting neurotransmitters at synaptic clefts has been particularly challenging due to their small size, low detection sensitivity, and the limited spatial resolution of current SRS techniques, impeding accurate mapping of their distribution and concentration. Recent advancements in ytterbium laser technology [11] have facilitated Femtosecond Fieldsocopy, a groundbreaking approach that offers super-resolution imaging with unparalleled selectivity, sensitivity, enhanced spectral coverage, and high contrast [10]. By addressing the limitations of existing methods, it promises to unlock new possibilities for sub-cellular research, allowing precise, label-free studies of molecular dynamics at previously unattainable scales.

Author contribution

SJ, AH, KS, AS have contributed equally in advancing Femtosecond Fieldsocopy.

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